

RUNNING HEAD: INTRAPROFESSIONAL ARGUMENTATION

Notes toward a theory of intraprofessional argumentation

Scholars who study professionalism often make an explicit claim that professions are ideologically homogenous and operate by enforced consensus. This assumption leaves no room for consideration of intraprofessional argumentation, and there is a dearth of scholarship that considers such controversy. I examine three elements common to most professions: autonomy, professional identity, and collegiality, and draw connections to the space for argument. I conclude by sketching the bare beginnings of a theory of co-constitutive argument.

Stephen Toulmin began his seminal work on informal logic (1958) by circumscribing his discussion with a core analogy to legal proceedings: "...forget about psychology, sociology, technology and mathematics . . . take as our model the discipline of jurisprudence. Logic (we may say) is generalised jurisprudence" (p. 7). Nearly a quarter century later, Toulmin focused his inquiry on the particular subset of logic that addressed moral and ethical questions, and had selected a second domain of reasoning for his pet synecdoche: "Once again, in other words, it was medicine -- as the first profession to which philosophers paid close attention during the new phase of 'applied ethics' that opened during the 1960s -- that set the example which was required in order to revive some important, and neglected, lines of argument within moral philosophy itself" (Toulmin, 1982, p. 746; see also Toulmin, 1981; Jonsen & Toulmin, 1990). Professor Toulmin is alive and well and serving on the faculty in the Anthropology Department at the University of Southern California, which means that the trifecta is in play. In the admittedly unlikely event that he offers up new research employing the reason-giving practices of *clergy* as an archetype¹, then he will have used all three of the occupational fields that fit comfortably within the definition of *professional* without substantial dissent: "There seems to be a consensus among sociologists only about doctors, lawyers and clergymen [sic], with all other occupations being up for debate" (Thakor & Kumar, 2000, p. 66).

Toulmin seems to be one of the few scholars willing to mention argument and any professional field in the same breath. The debate from the outside about what is and is not a profession is virtually the only specimen of debating mentioned in connection with this subject matter. In much scholarly work, professions are characterized as irreducible particles, similar to scientists' beliefs about molecules before they discovered atoms; atoms before they discovered protons, neutrons and electrons; and those subatomic particles before they discovered quarks. Hordes of researchers repeat the point that professions tend to adhere to norms of collegiality,

¹ Unless he hands his baton to Professor Lessl, one of my earliest instructors in rhetorical theory.

and that they work to maintain a monopoly over the work encompassed by their field of expertise, concluding from these premises that the only argument that members of a profession ever encounter are those between their spokespeople and the laity. There is, in the academic study of professions, a conspicuous absence of work that addresses argument *between* members of a profession, either as process or product (Wenzel, 1980). Evetts asserts that where professionals work through disagreement collectively, scholars of professionalism have treated the occurrence as an aberration to be fitted with its own exceptional explanation, rather than an expected and functional element of the system:

Much historical and contemporary analysis has been slow to incorporate this within-profession diversity into theorizing because of the prominence in analysis of entire, complete and whole professions and their professional projects to secure and maintain market and regulatory controls. These forms of analysis tended to assume that professional unity and common identity was the norm ... (1999, pp. 18-19).

Such a gap in the discussion, in itself, may motivate the aimlessly curious to attend to intraprofessional argument, but is unlikely to move the otherwise occupied. However, the list of defects plaguing existing investigations of the existence and effect of professions extends far beyond its neglect of argument. Eliot Freidson wrote in one of his final works on the subject (1994), "At present, I think it is fair to say that scholarship concerned with the professions is in an intellectual shambles" (p. 149). The state of assembled research within the field of communication is similarly incomplete:

These concepts are increasingly important to the areas of technical, professional, and business communication because in recent years these areas have been making claims toward and about professionalization. However, these discussions about professional communication have progressed largely without developing a robust and theoretically

sound framework for discussing issues about profession, professionalization, and professional power (Faber, 2002, p. 307).

Andrew Abbott, author of a seminal monograph on the "professional project" (1988), pointed the way toward the study of intraprofessional argument with two observations. First, he observed that the management of professional knowledge could not be properly understood if the tension of controversy was left out of the equation:

By focusing on parallels in organizational development, students of the professions lost sight of a fundamental fact of professional life – interprofessional competition. Control of knowledge and its applications means dominating outsiders who attack that control. Control without competition is trivial. Study of organizational forms can indeed show how certain occupations control their knowledge and its application. But it cannot tell why those forms emerge when they do or why they sometimes succeed and sometimes fail. Only the study of competition can accomplish that (pp. 1-2).

Abbott's first point addressed tension at the outer layer of a professional community: the interface between initiates and outsiders. However, elsewhere, he noted that the assumption of consensus among members of a profession was untenable: "Ignoring internal differentiation in professions has helped the professionalization concept simplify what it has to explain. But recent work implies that this assumption, too, is dangerous. . . . The development of internal differences is bound directly to the development of professionalism" (pp. 18-19).

The fact is, professionals argue among themselves. Doctors disagree over whether they should assist terminally ill patients in committing suicide (Hill, 1997), how donated organs ought to be allotted (Mishra, 1998), how dangerous salt intake is (Galewitz, 2007) and whether wellness programs have the potential to hold down spiraling health care costs (Yee, 2005). Lawyers disagree over whether they should breach confidentiality with their clients in order to

protect others from subsequent attacks (Savoie, 2001), whether the American Bar Association should sanction multi disciplinary practices (MDPs) that handle other professional services (Franken, 2000), and whether lawyers should have sex with their clients (Flood, 2000). Teachers argue about the best method for teaching cursive handwriting (Hammond, 1998), accountants differ over the potential effectiveness of heightened reporting standards (Armstrong, 1999), engineers disagree about the danger that low-powered FM radio stations will interfere with larger stations (Ahrens, 2000), and members of the clergy differ about everything from gay rights (Simpson, 2006) to the Iraq war (Kotkin & Speicher, 2003) to stem cell research (Rice, 2001). Any model of the development and function of professions that proceeds as though such disagreements do not occur, and that consensus is the normal state of affairs, suffers from debilitating flaws. Nearly fifty years ago, Bucher and Strauss warned, "We should also ask, wherever a profession seems to the general public to be relatively unified, why it seems so – for this, too, is a pertinent problem" (1961, p. 332).

Our need for an answer to the question is rather urgent, as professions are an important piece of the framework that holds modern civilization together. Koehn (1994) argues that they are "the only mechanism we have for collectively providing ourselves with the goods of health, legal justice, and spiritual peace We cannot simply hope that the sick, the accused or injured, and the spiritually needy will provide adequately for themselves" (p. 5). Cooper (2004) locates the need at the intersection of science and experience: "Because many of us are not only confused about technology but also about the meaning of our lives, increasingly we have to hire professionals not just because they have skills that serve our ends, but also because we need advice about the ends themselves" (p. 59). Cities expend effort, money and time to attract professionals to live inside their boundaries, because "If you're going to have the level of entrepreneurial growth that I think is healthy for a metropolitan area, you've got to attract young

professionals and continue to foster an entrepreneurial environment" (Dresang, 2004, p. D1), and university educators teach wave after wave of undergraduate students, most of whom plan to pursue an occupation that either identifies itself as a profession, or else is working to earn the heightened status and material rewards of that label. Wynia et al. (1999) conclude, "Professionalism is a structurally stabilizing, morally protective force in society. Along with private-sector and public or government activities, it is a cornerstone of a stable society" (p. 1612)

Despite this importance, or perhaps because of it, a confluence of forces is distorting the arrangement of authority and advances in knowledge that gave professional work a measure of predictability. Dent and Whitehead (2002) report that "The social and cultural assumptions that surround the term 'professional' have never been subject to so much question as they are now ... in this new era we are all expected to be professional, to perform professionally. In losing its exclusivity, being professional has become the *leitmotif* of the postmodern age" (p. 1). This development may be the culmination of a long-term appropriation of the prestige and profitability of professional status, identified thirty years ago by Blankenship: "We commonly hear about professional wrestling, professional crime, and doing a professional job. Mothers urge their children to enter the professions to better their life chances" (1977, p. 2). It may be that its ubiquity has diluted its potency, leading presidential candidate Mitt Romney to account for his passion for public service in the following terms: "But actually running for office as part of life only came to my mind because I had seen my dad and my mom do it. And they did it, not out of a sense of profession -- that they wanted to be professional politicians -- but out of a sense of duty, obligation to a country that they loved. And that's what got me involved in politics" (Woodruff, 2006, ¶ 28).

In the sections that follow, I will *not* attempt to impose argument on the scholarship of

professions as a unified theory. I will, however, consider three dynamics that influence the growth and continued existence of the phenomenon of professionalism: autonomy, professional identity, and collegiality. I will then offer a tentative sketch of several argumentative dynamics that influence the creation and maintenance of professionalism, and finally, articulate the tentative first claims of a theory of constitutive professional argument.

Key forces in the creation and renewal of professions

Professional autonomy

One of the primary features distinguishing professions from other occupations is an exceptionally high expectation of autonomy. Professionals devote much of their available negotiating leverage into issues of control of the work environment (Bucher & Stelling, 1977). Freidson identifies autonomy as the core feature of the phenomenon: "Professionalism, like the free market and bureaucracy, represents a method of organizing the performance of work. It differs from the free market and from bureaucracy in that it revolves around *the central principle that the members of a specialized occupation control their own work*" (1994, p. 73, emphasis in original). Professionals assert "the right to be the arbiters of their own work performance, justified by the claim that they are the only ones who know enough to be able to evaluate it properly," (p. 71).

This will to autonomy is entangled with argumentative messages and encounters in two senses. For many professionals, perhaps most typically doctors and members of the clergy, the work is not merely an occupation, but rather a *calling*, which imbues it with a protective ineffability that denies outsiders license to question their actions (May, 2001). Cooper observes that "In fact, we expect professionals to be so committed to the values their profession serves that it seems inappropriate to think they joined the profession for purely financial motives" (2004, p. 63), while Gustafson goes so far as to make a calling a prerequisite for *any* professional work

worthy of the name:

A "calling" without professionalization is bumbling, ineffective, and even dangerous. A profession without a calling, however, has no taps of moral and humane rootage to keep motivation alive, to keep human sensitivities and sensibilities alert, and to nourish a proper sense of self-fulfillment. Nor does a profession without a calling easily envision the larger ends and purposes of human good that our individual efforts can serve. The wider context of significance and meaning, both for ourselves and for others, easily withers away (1982, p. 514).

For some, this still leaves open the possibility of outside criticism, because one who does not fulfill the values of the profession simply ceases to belong among its number. Koehn explains that, to many critics, "being a professional is akin to being a parent. The parental practice of child-rearing exhibits a distinctive ethos where an ethos is understood as a characteristic devotion to a particular good. This ethos tends to define the practice: parents who do not take care of their children are not parenting" (1994, p. 3). However, argument is also the medium of maintenance when such attacks are deployed. Applbaum (1999) identifies a feature of professional authority which he labels *practice positivism*, or the plenary ability of professional practitioners to dictate the essence of their professional role. Pursuing an extended illustration bearing on doctors, Applbaum argues that if outsiders make demands of those who practice medicine that become intolerable, the doctors are free to rename their pursuit: "they may come to see themselves as schmectors of various stripes. And if enough of them think so, *it will become so*: a new set of social meanings surrounding a new actual role, the role of schmector, will have emerged" (p. 59). He concludes that doctors themselves must settle such challenges among themselves, as a closed community:

The profession of doctoring must therefore understand itself as a calling that could have

been otherwise, but argue why it still is a calling worthy of being answered by a reflective practitioner ... The challenge, of course, is to continue to articulate in a clear and reasoned voice to both doctors and patients what would be lost if the practice of doctoring gave way, in substantial measure, to the various forms of schmooching that I have described (p. 60).

Professionals thus carefully regulate the conditions of entry to argument, declining to acknowledge others' judgments of their truth claims or their practice. If they do grapple with controversial issues, their participation is truncated by a limited commitment to change based on the outcome of deliberation, and any such deliberation is confined entirely to a cloistered pocket of the technical sphere. Matters of public *concern* may contribute to the substance of such disputes, but public *participation* is not welcome.

Professional identity

A consequence of the professional *calling* is the existence of a profession as its own very robust element of *identity*. As Gustafson explains, "One is a 'member' of a profession; one 'belongs' to his or her profession. It is an important mark of one's personal and social identity" (1982, p. 507). This commitment may in some cases be a silent and personal choice made by the professional, but more often is evident to family, friends and onlookers as well. Moline (1986) further observes that "We contrast professionals with people who have an occupation, trade, or job rather than a calling. We speak of what the barber or computer expert '*does* for a living.' We speak of what the paradigm professional *is* -- a physician, barrister, priest or rabbi" (p. 502). The identity element is not often neutral: professional status is an identifier to which people *aspire*. Gary Fine points out that a professional identity carries its own inflationary momentum: people return again and again to their professional identity, and build it up and bolster it and backstop it because of the positive reinforcement it supplies: "When one sees oneself as a professional, one's

identity is likely to be self-enhancing. Unlike the rhetoric of manual labor, which divides one's work and personal self, professionalism merges work and self; pride in one's achievement is crucial" (1996, p. 100). He concludes that, "When occupational identification is high, professional rhetoric is likely – little is more important than the work. Professional rhetoric does not occur constantly, but it is particularly likely when a worker feels that it is his or her presence that contributes to successful production" (p. 100).

Despite this, professional alignments are not themselves ordained by immutable features of the natural world. Very commonly, insiders and outsiders preface their observations with reference to "one's *chosen* profession." It is easy to forget that they are the product of human choice; however, some scholars conceive of professions primarily, or even entirely, as instructional profiles or ideal types. Heaphy, Sanchez-Burkes & Ashford argue that "Although the term 'professional' is invoked as if it were clear, the criteria contained within the mental schema of professionalism are actually based on a variety of tacit, culturally grounded assumptions about what is appropriate and inappropriate at work" (2006, p. 4), concluding that "professionalism schemas include knowledge about the attributes of a prototypical person who is professional" (p. 7). The identity construction is not entirely free-form; the autonomy discussed in the prior section may insulate professionals from argumentative engagement with outsiders, but their identity incorporation is vulnerable to the residues of past settled controversies deposited by their mentors and other predecessors. Hilton and Slotnick (2005) pinpoint the moment of emergence of a fledgling professional's newfound identity as a moment at which dependence on colleagues is particularly acute: "...protoprofessionalism is about developing identity (i.e. what a person does and the ways in which that person relates to others)" (p. 62). Arguments exchanged within the ambit of one's profession thus carry an adhesive quality, a non-detachability, that distinguishes them from arguments between workers in other occupations.

Choosing to *do* something, to carry out an act or set of actions, entails a far milder commitment than making an explicit claim to *be* something, to assert that a trait constitutes a portion of one's essence.

Collegiality

Having partitioned non-initiates out of the discourse with the demand for autonomy, and filled in the enclosed space with the content of a professional identity, members of a profession finally extend their activity into a mesh of mutually supporting cooperative ventures, consultations, and reviews, all of which fulfill the function of *collegiality*. Autonomy requires a check, and crafting of an identity requires the existence of *other* identities, distinct and similar, to contextualize it, and the role of collegiality in the makeup of a profession fills both functions. Moore observes that,

Both among the high-ranking professional occupations, and, perhaps even more noticeably, among those attempting to gain full professional acceptance, there is a strong and normatively supported tendency to emphasize the collegiality of the occupation.

Terms such as "colleague," "fellow," and even "brother" abound as references to peers, particularly before the laity (1970, p. 109).

It is the support of colleagues that is the currency of a professional's authority. Cooper explains that "professionals should be able to explain to others the reasoning behind their use of discretion. If you cannot give a responsible account to other members of your profession that justifies how you used your power to make a discretionary decision, then maybe you weren't making a professional decision at all" (2004, p. 69). This ingrained pattern of support and reinforcement works synergistically with autonomy claims to create the *appearance* of an immovable consensus among professionals, and thus, a rather barren ground for argument: "An extreme manifestation of collegiality is the reluctance to criticize the judgment or skill of a

fellow professional" (Moore, 1970, p. 110). However, that appearance can be deceiving.

Freidson observes that the permafrost of professional solidarity has come under the influence of its own global warming, and begun to shift:

... it used to be difficult to get professionals to testify against a colleague in malpractice suits. Furthermore, the disciplinary boards maintained by professional associations, as well as those attached to state licensing boards, seemed to act slowly, if at all, in response to consumer complaints. They seldom censured their colleagues and revoked their licenses even less frequently. Political pressures have now forced the professions to be more active in such affairs, thus setting colleague against colleague (1994, pp. 141-142).

Professional work thus takes place within a murmur of exchanged messages between colleagues. Their feedback is the ground of authority, the reminder of identity, and the most frequently employed safeguard against malpractice. And, as other conditions cultivate a fertile communicative ground for controversy, the channel of colleague-talk becomes the conduit through which arguments circulate.

My purpose in this section has not been to attempt to define or explain what a profession is, does, or is not. The three themes discussed here are constant topics in past scholarship of the professions, but they are not constituent parts of a complete model. Rather, they are powerful forces that combine to position members of a profession in any argumentative encounter. They are co-influential, joining in permutations to lay the foundation for professional argument: autonomy limits the professional arguer's degree of commitment, while identity intensifies it along a different axis, as the identified professional is not free to dismiss an argumentative position as trivial or unimportant in other spheres of activity. Autonomy also shuts out certain participants as noninitiates, while collegiality places a powerful obligation upon the professional to attend to others. Starr warns, "A professional who yields too much to the demands of clients

violates an essential article of the professional code: Quacks, as Everett Hughes once defined them, are practitioners who continue to please their customers but not their colleagues" (1982, p. 23). Finally, identity and collegiality reinforce and reflect one another: Bucher & Strauss note that "Collegueship may be one of the most sensitive indicators of segmentation within a profession. Whom a man [sic] considers to be his colleagues is ultimately linked with his own place within his profession" (1961, p. 330). These long-studied and heavily-documented reoccurring tendencies among members of a profession prepare the ground for the particular argumentative practices in play.

Dynamics of argument in intraprofessional deliberation

Content and relational dimensions of intraprofessional argument

At times, professionals disagree on the content, the specialized and protected knowledge, that is the substance of their practice. McDonald offers the needed reminder that "Professions are knowledge-based occupations and therefore the nature of their knowledge, the socio-cultural evaluation of their knowledge and the occupation's strategies in handling their knowledge base are of central importance" (1995, p. 160). Freidson identifies an "activity of some importance that is encouraged by professionalism," namely "Research and theorizing that threaten the foundation of the practical work of normal science become possible, as does questioning the legitimacy of conventional practices and policies (1994, p. 176-177). Naturally, such questions on many occasions stir spirited dissent from those who doubt the challenge or prefer the conventional practice. Where these disputes break into open controversy, there are collective expectations and procedures that contain and discipline the disagreements, shoring up the collegial network and the parameter of autonomy. Larson (1990) insists "that there is a 'properly' or 'typically professional' mode of addressing conflictive issues that can be included within the profession's discursive field," and that it includes "the norm of containing controversy within the

field or, which is equivalent, the normative protection of its boundaries," as well as "the defence of professional authority, the tendency to de-authorize non-expert speakers even when the issue at hand regards them" (pp. 39-40).

Not all substantive disagreement focuses solely upon the profession's body of knowledge. Many scholars have asserted that an occupation's most critical step toward acquiring professional status is the adoption of an ethical code. Medicine, one of the most ancient professions, proudly displays the Hippocratic oath as one of its founding texts (Markel, 2004; Lucas & Pross, 1995), even though the actual oath is too controversial to be administered to students without radical excisions (Colburn, 1991). Derr (1986) identifies the espousal of ethical principles as the activity that brings the gerund "profession" into existence: "The term 'profession' or 'ethical profession' is used because the qualified physician or attorney must in fact *profess* a specific set of normative or ethical commitments" (p. 29). Roberts & Dietrich (1999) assert that professional ethics is the substance of the network binding individual practitioners together into a social institution: "We can think of ethics as providing the link between the individual professional and the professions as institutions that have a role and position in wider society" (p. 989). Cooper concludes that because the ethical principles serve as the profession's essence, it is impossible to arrive at a theory of professionalism without affording the ethical decisionmaking a central place:

Since a profession's code of ethics prescribes how professional practice ought to be conducted, to evaluate the adequacy of general professional practice we will need to investigate the rationality of the background norms used to justify codes of ethics. This means that an adequate definition of professionalism will be normative, since it will point to the general ideals that influence the prescriptions given in professional codes (2004, p. 58).

Finally, Moore identifies questions of ethical practice as the convergence of the three factors

already discussed: autonomy, identity and collegiality. "Aside from the circumstance that standards must be established and codes adopted, a professional body is not a universal mutual-policing organization. Individual self-policing and informal policing by colleagues are likely in fact to be the most effective agencies of control" (1970, p. 127).

It would be a mistake to believe that the identification of ethics as the kernel of professionalism lends it discursive inertia, enabling it to serve as a brake on change. In fact, comforting illusions aside, virtually every profession continually manicures and reinvents its ethical code as the state of professional problem and professional practice evolves on the wavefront of broader social change. The changes are forged in a process of reason-giving, and the strength and convicting force of reasons offered is the driver of change. Frankel grounds this tendency in the *process* by which professionals deliberate about their ethical principles, explaining that that "It would be unfortunate if the emphasis on a code of ethics as a product obscured the value of the process by which a code is developed and subsequently revised. This process is a time of critical self-examination by both individual members and the profession as a whole" (1989, p. 112) and concluding, "Moral authority does not inhere in a paper document, but rather in the weight of reasons that accompanies arguments for or against certain actions" (p. 114).

Intraprofessional deliberation on ethical principles is one among many factors that may move the collegial relationship toward dissensus and dispute while nevertheless exerting a constructive influence. A profession's ethical code may remain as an archival record not only of the substance of disagreement, but of the alignment of arguers that gained or lost critical mass at moments in its history. Bucher and Strauss explain that,

These products of professional activity are not necessarily evidence of internal homogeneity and consensus but rather of the power of certain groups: established

associations become battlegrounds as different emerging segments compete for control. Considered from this viewpoint, such things as codes of ethics and procedures of certification become the historical deposits of certain powerful segments (1961, pp. 331-332).

And Freidson reports that in a departure from a former pattern of foot-dragging by professional associations against addressing allegations of ethical breaches, "Political pressures have now forced the professions to be more active in such affairs, thus setting colleague against colleague" (1994, pp. 141-142). These divisions tend to track at least three identified fault lines. Becher, explaining the gap that may open between teachers and practitioners of a profession, concludes that "the shared area of knowledge is thus seen from distinct perspectives by those whose prime task it is to inculcate it and by those mainly concerned to apply it in their daily lives" (1990, p. 146). McDonald concurs that striking the right balance between knowledge derived from practice and knowledge constructed as theory is a fussy and never-completed process: "At either extreme, the profession tends to lose credibility; too great abstraction appears to be mere formalism, to great concreteness is judged to be no more than a craft. At some nicely chosen spot in the middle, the possessor of knowledge and technique can successfully exercise professional judgment" (1995, p. 165). Specialization may also split professionals from their homogeneity into segments; Leicht and Fennell observe that as professionals discover centers of profit or prestige within their area of practice, and declare themselves specialists, moving away from their colleagues by partitioning their identity into its own pocket, "the different work foci of these three professional groups produce cleavages within the larger profession, which reverberate through issues such as professional identity, governance of the profession, and definitions of professional interests" (2001, p. 134). Bucher and Strauss find a third grain of potential schism in the hierarchies that develop in the sanctioning bodies:

Those who control the professional associations also control the organs of public relations. They take on the role of spokesmen [sic] to the public, interpreting the position of the profession, as they see it. They also negotiate with relevant special publics. The outsider coming into contact with the profession tends to encounter the results of the inner group's efforts; he does not necessarily become aware of the inner circle or the power struggles behind the unified front (1961, p. 332).

Tempting though it may be to follow the momentum of Bucher and Strauss' cautionary notes to a sweeping dismissal of intraprofessional discourse as a power game, unconcerned with the convicting force of reason-giving, it remains the case that between the checking force of collegiality and the centrality of specialized professional knowledge and technique to arguer identity, the primary playing field for the ambitious members of a profession remains argument with their colleagues. Starr concludes, "For it is almost always to argument, rather than coercion, that independent professionals turn when their authority fails" (1982, p. 11).

Giddens, Ehninger, and the argumentatively-constructed professional as structure

Initiates of a profession operate within a cloistered community that is impervious to challenges from outside, that equips them with contours of identity to overlay on top of their pre-existing elements, and that places them in a network of interdependent actors who legitimate their authority claims by supporting one another. This set of resources is brought into being through the ongoing practice of the profession, and also enables the profession's continued survival. It thus conforms remarkably well to Anthony Giddens' account of structuration. Giddens explains that "The constitution of agents and structures are not two independently given sets of phenomena, a dualism, but represent a duality. According to the notion of the duality of structure, the structural properties of social systems are both medium and outcome of the practices they recursively organize" (1984, p. 25). Freidson outlines the created and constraining

effect of professional expectations and norms in terms that are a tight fit with Giddens' theory: "One does not attempt to determine what profession is in an absolute sense so much as how people in a society determine who is a professional and who is not, how they 'make' or 'accomplish' professions by their activities, and what the consequences are for the way in which they see themselves and perform their work" (1994, p. 20). Fournier concurs: "Professionals are the target of professional rationality, they are both the governor and the governed" (1999, pp. 284-285). Blankenship explains that it is the performance of willingly subjecting oneself to the constraints adopted by one's colleagues that brings the profession into existence: "When a number of persons agree to the existence and legitimacy of a profession and then act accordingly, using the symbolic profession to account for their activities and give meaning to their activities, the consequence is the construction of the profession as a social object" (1977, p. 10). Dent and Whitehead conclude:

... whatever power the professional or manager might be able to exercise, it is only enabled through them engaging in and reproducing those dominant truths about how professionals and managers should be, though these truths and knowledges are not themselves fixed, and are subject to influence and change (2002, p. 10).

Even though the institution of a profession may in some cases be abstract and intangible, with licensing and membership requirements that vary from strict to nonexistent, the accountability to colleagues and embrace of an archetypal identity are girders that form the truss of the profession, and therefore maintain both the area and limits of its practice.

Ehninger's (1970) consideration of argument as *method* draws together many, if not all, of the threads traced to this point. He points out that each arguer's persona is both expressed and endangered: "...because argument is 'person-risking' it is 'person-making.' By accepting the risks implicit in an attitude of restrained partisanship the arguer both bestows 'personhood' on his [sic]

opponent and gains 'personhood' for himself" (p. 109). The exchanged personhoods are the professional identities: one professional recirculates the identity markers in her own practice, while shoring up the identities of her colleagues (and they hers) through consultation, thus renewing the resource for future use. Collegiality and autonomy are the sharp defining moves that construct and maintain the channels through which the arguments are delivered. Finally, the articulated and endangered collaborators filter their shared pool of knowledge by identifying errors: "Argument in short, instead of being an enterprise in instruction, is an exercise in correction. Its purpose is not to extend knowledge, but to reform and to purify it" (p. 100). Brint confirms the presence of this trait in professional communities: "Professionals ... are more likely to find congenial efforts to synthesize and balance opposed political and value positions" (1994, p. 12). Mutual acknowledgment and mutual correction proceed along congruent and interwoven tracks.

Constitutive argument within professions

From the preceding, I arrive now at the central claim of this investigation: professionals are enabled and constrained in their arguments with other professionals by their persona, which consists of a person set apart (autonomy), a person qualified to practice (professional identity), and a person recognized as a learned sibling (colleague). The persona and arguments are *co-constitutive*, meaning that as the persona changes, the arsenal of arguments that may be deployed changes, and as the arguments proceed through rounds of modification, mutual correction, rebuttal and rejoinder, they change the contours of the persona.

If attorneys collectively endorse the notion that no attorney may reveal confidential information disclosed by a client, then that fiduciary responsibility is a major constituent element of the archetypal "attorney." They bring that assumption, its entailments, and a record of conformity and disciplinary hearings for breaches, into any discussion of whether exceptions are

acceptable. When they debate exceptions, they place at risk the accrued trust and expectations that clients have acquired through decades of practice and uncounted millions of transactions, and must calibrate the desirability of their proposals against the scale of that risk. If, as an outcome of their argument, they modify the requirement and permit one another to reveal information in cases where a third party is at risk of injury, then something fundamental about what it is to be an attorney has changed.

The assemblage of assertions backed by specialized knowledge claims, circulated in an economy of mutual correction through networks of colleagues, interrupted by segmentations that serve as sites for in-field controversy, is a set of dynamics without which it is impossible to grasp the functioning of professions. I do not claim that this is a complete, sufficient theory of how, when, and why occupations make the transition to, through, and from professional status, but I do assert that scholarship that focuses *solely* on jurisdiction, monopoly, organizational patterns, power, and other by-products of professionalism, while overstating the homogeneity and apparent consensus maintained by members of a profession, offers only a crippled account of the phenomenon it describes. The work outlined here is a necessary complement, a fusion of elements of substance and arrangement, an explanation of how knowledge is managed and adapted through change, and a more robust portrayal of the origin and fortification of professional identity elements.

Professionals do more than argue, but they do argue. Argumentation is a key missing piece in the scholarship of professions. Through argument, professionals practice their calling, construct and maintain their identity, manage relationships with their colleagues, and create and renew the resources of authority and leadership upon which they draw to sustain the necessary conditions of their work. If something about the work of two of the three paradigm professions drew Toulmin's attention, but repelled the attention of scholars of professionalism for the better

part of a century, then between that affiliation and repulsion lies an enormous swath of ground long overdue for exploration.

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